

UNDERSTANDING THE SOURCES OF JOB SATISFACTION AMONG PRIVATE TEACHERS: A MULTIVARIATE ANALYSIS

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This research paper looks into the various sources of job satisfaction among high school teachers in a private institution. The study employed a complete enumeration in choosing the participants and considered primary information in the data gathering. The collected data were analyzed using descriptive measures, exploratory factor and principal component analyses, and K-means clustering. Results suggested that, on average, teachers are moderately satisfied ($M=3.34$; $SD=0.67$) working in a private institution. Exploratory factor analysis identified two primary sources of job satisfaction: (a) Working Environment and Fulfillment and (b) Rewards and Social Relationships, with the former exerting a greater influence. Principal component analysis further revealed that supervision is a major contributing factor to satisfaction within the working environment and fulfillment dimension, whereas recognition plays a significant role in satisfaction associated with rewards and social relationships. Moreover, the K-means clustering portrayed that about 5.88% of the private teachers have low job satisfaction (Cluster 1), 50% are moderately satisfied (Cluster 2), and 44.12% are highly satisfied (Cluster 3). Conclusively, private teachers' job satisfaction can vary depending on various factors, particularly in work assignments and school management. Hence, the study highly recommends that to improve private teachers' job satisfaction, a rewards system and work environment must be reinforced, which boosts their welfare and interests.

Keywords: Private teachers, job satisfaction, work environment, multivariate analysis

JEL Classification codes: D74, H41, O10

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Received: November 24, 2025 | Revised: December 30, 2025 | Accepted: December 31, 2025

1. INTRODUCTION

Globally, teacher job satisfaction has emerged as a critical concern in education systems given its close links to instructional quality, teacher retention, and student learning outcomes across both developed and developing contexts. International studies consistently report that teachers' professional well-being is influenced by economic conditions, institutional support, workload demands, and opportunities for career development, rendering job satisfaction a multidimensional and context-dependent construct (Toropova et al., 2021). Meanwhile, private school teachers across the globe contribute to student growth by helping them academically and become future builders in society. The shortage of teacher personnel in private institutions compels educators to handle additional administrative work, such as advising students and planning events. In fact, most teachers signed with short-term contracts make up the workforce, while job insecurity causes career instabilities and work-related stress (Adu-Baffoe & Bonney, 2021; Mushtaque et al., 2022). In addition, with strict institutional policies in place, private schools demand that their educators maintain high academic standards and meet disciplinary requirements, which results in teachers' burnout (Yang et al., 2024). In that case, Noori (2023) depicted that private teachers have less job satisfaction level as opposed to public educators. Job satisfaction in teaching is an emotion that refers to contentment and with high regard to imparting knowledge to students, which emphasizes a sense of purpose (Mendoza, 2024; Olaifa et al., 2024). Private school educators find satisfaction in both their teaching allegiance and believing in workplace environments and organizational embracement, despite facing work obstacles. When teachers inspire students through collaborative curriculum development while maintaining personal connections with their students, they establish their professional satisfaction (León et al., 2021). Apparently, enhanced teaching engagement stems from both lower student-to-teacher ratios combined with controlled classroom environments, which make the work maximally satisfying for educators (Sivakami & Elayaraja, 2024).

The maintenance of satisfied and dedicated teachers in all private schools depends on adequate support systems for staff alongside professional growth opportunities and appropriate recognition programs (Ismail & David, 2024). However, Nir and Naphcha, M. (2007) portrayed that private teachers must cope with reduced pay and heavier work responsibilities combined with professional threats, yet public education teachers do not have to manage these issues. The professional landscape for private school educators includes economic restrictions, together with institutional requirements and teaching standards. Research reveals that teaching in private schools earns teachers less money than their public-school counterparts because of funding

inequalities leading to unstable employment, limited professional advancement potential, and higher turnover rates (Imran & Ahmed, 2020; Ismail & David, 2024). Moreover, private school instructors handle a heavy workload that includes teaching responsibilities alongside administrative work and student guidance, along with extracurricular tasks, resulting in high occupational stress and eventual burnout. In fact, job satisfaction arises from both internal teaching motivations and external workplace influences such as administrative encouragement and collegial support, along with institutional backing (Olaifa et al., 2024). In addition, teaching experiences receive better support from small classes combined with disciplinary structure, as well as opportunities for professional advancement, together with education and rest opportunities that create high job satisfaction (Adu-Baffoe & Bonney, 2021). Research into private school teachers' work environments and job satisfaction has yielded many results, yet several critical gaps persist. Studies demonstrate that private school teachers earn less and must handle heavier workloads, yet research fails to show how these challenges differ between religious schools, non-sectarian schools, and international schools (Sahito & Vaisanen, 2020). Studies lack a thorough analysis of how temporary contracts influence teacher career growth, as well as their mental health conditions and financial security prospects. Research into job satisfaction concentrates on fundamental elements, including compensation levels, along with workload limitations and support from school administration (Williams, 2022). The research community lacks sufficient studies that examine how teachers interpret job satisfaction based on their cultural backgrounds and local conditions, as well as institutional settings. Research studies highlight external motivators such as financial rewards but fail to offer a sufficient understanding of how internal elements developing throughout an educator's career evolve, such as teacher autonomy, teaching passion, and professional identity growth (Zhou et al., 2024). The research on what satisfies private school educators about their jobs faces challenges because it lacks comprehension of how inter-generational disparities affect teaching satisfaction factors.

Research needs to delve deeper into how new approaches to professional development mentoring programs and school leadership methods affect teacher job satisfaction rates alongside teacher retention (Ortan et al., 2021; Koehler & Olds, 2022). The research contains limited evidence regarding how job satisfaction influences teacher performance, together with student outcomes and the sustainability of institutions over extended periods. Research to investigate these gaps offers an opportunity to build a better understanding of boosting private school teachers' job quality and general welfare conditions. Hence, this study was conducted. Generally, the study characterizes the different sources of job satisfaction among private teachers. Specifically, the paper aims

to answer the following objectives: (i) to measure the level of perception among private teachers in regard to different sources of job satisfaction; (ii) to group the various sources with respect to the teachers' perception; and (iii) to cluster the teachers according to their perception of the different sources of job satisfaction. The study of private school teachers' working conditions and job satisfaction, alongside its defining sources, enables educators to serve administrators, policymakers, and researchers in their efforts. It delivers insights that can create strategies to maintain teacher retention while improving their welfare in the face of salary shortages, heavy responsibilities, and constant career threats. The development of workload distribution policies, compensation systems, and support strategies falls to administrators and policymakers, who must create fair employment standards and professional development initiatives. Research into job satisfaction origins gives educational institutions tools for implementing strategies to boost teacher motivation and school performance that benefit student learning. Through filling important gaps in existing research, the study contributes to our understanding of teaching motivations in private schools with a focus on sustainable and equitable educational approaches.

2. FRAMEWORK OF THE STUDY

Teachers' workplace well-being and work experience mainly result from fundamental satisfaction factors. The institutional elements comprise salary dimensions and job security, together with work environment characteristics and institutional policy standards (Ortan & Simut, 2021; Casinillo et al., 2025). Environmental factors of teaching emphasize how teachers view their work through the lens of workload, along with professional advancement prospects, recognition, plus career potential for growth. The combination of professional and personal factors creates essential conditions that form teachers' motivation levels and occupational satisfaction (Toropova et al., 2021). Special personal factors include work-life balance and student-teacher relations, along with teaching autonomy and personal connections between teachers and their school community. Systematic analysis shows that teacher commitment occurs through emotional involvement in educational work together with adjustable work commitments (Park & Lee, 2023). Each satisfaction source receives classification according to teachers' perceived satisfaction levels through three different groups. Highly satisfied teachers rate the three satisfaction domains both at professional and personal levels, and within institutional structures, positively. The teachers demonstrate deep job satisfaction along with high work motivation and connection to their professional roles. Teachers who maintain moderate satisfaction report positive and negative professional encounters

throughout their various workplace elements. Uncontented educators demonstrate low job satisfaction because they lack satisfaction regarding institutional backing and professional chances, as well as personal fulfillment. Hence, the research framework examines different job satisfaction factors for private school educators through factor analysis and clustering approaches. The framework consists of two primary components: grouping the satisfaction factors and then conducting cluster analysis to distinguish different satisfaction degrees among private teachers.

Figure 1. Conceptual model

3. METHODOLOGY

Research Design

A quantitative method was utilized in this current paper to characterize the different sources of job satisfaction among private teachers. The focus of the paper is to give a valuable description of the sources of job satisfaction, to group the said sources according to their statistical characteristics, and to cluster the private teachers in regard to their perception scores. Henceforth, this paper employed a multivariate analysis research design to answer the research objectives and achieve its goal. Multivariate data analysis is a kind of statistical method that involves multiple variables that are analyzed at once to elucidate the relationships and their characteristics between them. In addition, the goal of the research design is to provide a statistical argument and information that explains the private teachers' well-being and eliminates turnover intention.

Respondents, Sampling Technique, and Ethical Procedure

Among the Provinces of Leyte, Philippines, Jaro and Abuyog are the municipalities with highly performing private high schools, namely Notre Dame of Jaro, Inc. (NDJI) and Notre Dame of Abuyog, Inc. (NDAI), respectively. These private schools are well-known as the topmost dynamic and achiever sectarian schools and are managed by the oblates of Notre Dame in Leyte (Lleve et al., 2024). However, these two private schools are known to have a higher rate of teacher turnover every year. In that case, the researchers are motivated to investigate private teachers' job satisfaction as one of the important indicators of turnover intention. Hence, the target population of interest in this study is all the teachers in NDJI and NDAI. Now, since there are only a few private teachers in the said high schools, the study employed complete enumeration or census. It is worth noting that the census survey method ensures the accuracy of the results and eliminates the bias that may potentially exist. Hence, a total of 34 private teachers were considered as respondents of the study, comprising 12 NDJI teachers and 22 NDAI teachers. Note that this study carefully takes into account an ethical procedure in research. In that case, prior to the conduct of the survey, the researchers secured a formal consent letter addressed to the principals of two private schools. When the principals agreed to the survey study, another letter was sent to the private teachers informing them of the purpose and benefits of the outcome of the research. In addition, teachers are informed that participation in the survey is voluntary and anonymity is guaranteed to protect their privacy. Moreover, private teachers were also informed that there were no sensitive and offensive questions during the survey, and data privacy was strictly observed.

Research Questionnaire and Data Collection Process

A developed structured questionnaire was used in this study as an instrument for gathering useful data to answer the research objectives. The questionnaire is constructed based on the paper by Ololube (2006), which captures the different sources of job satisfaction that motivate teachers to do their work assignments. The purpose of the said questionnaire is to gather information that explains the sources of job satisfaction that may suggest some arguments that reduce the turnover rate in private schools and may give a plan of action or policy for school effectiveness. This study considered 10 sources of job satisfaction for teachers. In that case, the developed questionnaire contains 10 sections, where each section represents one source of job satisfaction and each section contains scale questions. So, the 10 sections are the following: (1) School and administration policies (with 8 questions), (2) Supervision (with 5 questions), (3) Salary

and Benefits (with 6 questions), (4) Interpersonal Relations (with 3 questions), (5) Working Conditions (with 4 questions), (6) Work Itself (with 3 questions), (7) Achievement (with 4 questions), (8) Recognition (with 4 questions), (9) Responsibility (with 4 questions), Advancement (with 4 questions). Each question follows a 5-point rating scale with a corresponding verbal response and description. Table 1 presents the possible mean perception scores of teachers in each item question.

Table 1. Teachers' perception score, response, and their verbal description

Mean score	Response	Verbal description
1.00 - 1.80	Strong disagree	Very dissatisfied
1.81 - 2.60	Disagree	Dissatisfied
2.61 - 3.40	Neutral	Moderately satisfied
3.41 - 4.20	Agree	Satisfied
4.21 - 5.00	Strongly agree	Very satisfied

In validating the questionnaire, three experts in social science (PhD holders) have scrutinized and evaluated the content. In that case, they have found that the instrument is valid and accurate to capture the teachers' well-being and job satisfaction level in a private institution. Moreover, the research instrument has also been tested for reliability using Cronbach's Alpha (Cronbach, 1951) and found that the scale coefficient can be interpreted as a reliable and good set of questions, as shown in Table 2. Hence, the sources of the job satisfaction questionnaire are consistently good in measuring the desired information in the survey.

Table 2. Reliability test for the sources of job satisfaction variables.

Sources of job satisfaction	Number of items	Reliability coefficient
School and administration policies	8	0.913
Supervision	5	0.950
Salary and Benefits	6	0.904
Interpersonal Relations	3	0.767
Working Conditions	4	0.847
Work Itself	3	0.893
Achievement	4	0.843
Recognition	4	0.917
Responsibility	4	0.851
Advancement	4	0.872

Statistical Methods and Data Analysis

When the survey was completed, the data gathered were encoded in Microsoft Excel and underwent cleaning, in which outliers were removed. In summarizing the data to give an appropriate description, standard descriptive metrics were calculated, such as mean (M), standard deviation (SD), minimum and maximum value, and rank. Moreover, the data in this study were analyzed using JASP software and various multivariate statistical techniques, including factor analysis, principal component analysis (PCA), and K-means cluster analysis. Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) was conducted using the Principal Axis Factoring technique with varimax rotation to identify the underlying factors influencing job satisfaction among private teachers. The Eigenvalue greater than 1 criterion was used to determine the number of factors to retain. To assess the suitability of the dataset for factor analysis, the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) statistic was calculated. According to Kaiser (1974), a KMO value above 0.5 indicates that the sample is adequate for factor analysis. Additionally, Bartlett's Test of Sphericity was performed to confirm that the inter-item correlations were sufficiently strong to justify factor analysis. A factor loading threshold of greater than 0.5 was adopted, following the recommendations of previous studies (Hulland, 1999; Stevens, 2002), to ensure meaningful associations between variables and extracted factors. In addition, Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was employed to quantify the influence of job satisfaction components on the identified factors. Finally, K-means clustering was conducted to group teachers based on their job satisfaction components, enabling the identification of distinct clusters within the datasets.

4. RESULTS

Descriptive Statistics

Table 3 shows that teachers are moderately satisfied with the private institutions' "Supervision (M=3.17; SD=1.03)", "Salary and benefits (M=3.04; SD=0.79)", "Interpersonal relations (M=3.31; SD=0.74)", "Recognition (M=2.75; SD=0.92)", "Responsibility (M=3.10; SD=0.87)", "Advancement (M=3.14; SD=0.92)." Meanwhile, private teachers are satisfied with their "School and administration policies (M=3.72; SD=0.79)", "Working conditions (M=3.47; SD=0.88)", "Work itself (M=3.81; SD=0.77)", and "Achievement (M=3.78; SD=0.72)." Overall, the job satisfaction perception score of private teachers is close to 3.34 (SD=0.67) and can be interpreted as "Moderately satisfied."

Table 3. Private teachers’ sources of job satisfaction

Sources of job satisfaction	Mean	SD	Description	Rank
School and administration policies	3.72	0.79	Satisfied	3
Supervision	3.17	1.03	Moderately satisfied	6
Salary and benefits	3.04	0.79	Moderately satisfied	9
Interpersonal relations	3.31	0.74	Moderately satisfied	5
Working conditions	3.47	0.88	Satisfied	4
Work itself	3.81	0.77	Satisfied	1
Achievement	3.78	0.72	Satisfied	2
Recognition	2.75	0.92	Moderately satisfied	10
Responsibility	3.10	0.87	Moderately satisfied	8
Advancement	3.14	0.92	Moderately satisfied	7
Total	3.34	0.67	Moderately satisfied	

Exploratory Factor Analysis on Job Satisfaction Sources

According to the analysis, the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) statistic of 0.904 indicates that the sample size is highly adequate for factor analysis, providing a robust basis for extracting meaningful factors. Additionally, Bartlett’s test of sphericity ($\chi^2 = 218.697$, $df = 45$, $p\text{-value} < 0.001$) confirms that the correlation matrix is significantly different from an identity matrix, thus validating the appropriateness of applying factor analysis to the data set [4]. Factor analysis was conducted on the scores of ten job satisfaction components among private school teachers to identify the underlying dimensions influencing job satisfaction. The results of the factor analysis, with varimax rotation applied, are presented in Table 1, highlighting a cumulative variance explained of 67.1%, which suggests that the extracted factors account for a substantial proportion of the variance in the dataset.

The analysis identified two distinct factors contributing to job satisfaction: Working Environment and Fulfillment (Factor 1) and Rewards and Social Relationships (Factor 2). Working Environment includes components such as working conditions (C1), school and administration policies (C2), responsibility (C3), achievement (C4), work itself (C5), and supervision (C6). These variables exhibited high positive loadings on Factor 1, indicating that higher scores on these components are strongly associated with a more favorable perception of the working environment. On the other hand, Rewards and Social Relationship encompasses supervision (C6), recognition (C7), salary and benefits (C8), advancement (C9), and interpersonal relationships (C10). Variables associated with Factor

2 also demonstrated strong positive loadings, signifying that higher scores on these components correlate with greater satisfaction related to rewards and social relationships. Notably, supervision (C6) loads positively on both factors, reflecting its dual role in influencing both the working environment and professional growth. Overall, the results suggest a two-dimensional structure of job satisfaction among private school teachers, with the factors reflecting distinct yet interrelated aspects of their professional experiences.

Table 4. Varimax Rotated Factor Matrix of the Job Satisfaction Components Displaying a Two-Factor Model.

Components	Factor 1	Factor 2	Uniqueness
Working Conditions	0.718		0.163
School and administration policies	0.700		0.221
Responsibility	0.673		0.149
Achievement	0.599		0.111
Work Itself	0.563		0.328
Supervision	0.437	0.485	0.339
Recognition		0.908	0.214
Salary and Benefits		0.652	0.227
Advancement		0.508	0.335
Interpersonal Relations		0.464	0.285
<i>Eigenvalues</i>	2.634	2.207	
<i>% Var</i>	0.365	0.306	

Principal Component Analysis of the Two Factors

Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was conducted on the variables associated with the two identified factors to assess the contribution of each variable to the overall structure. Table 2 presents the weights (eigenvectors) of each variable on the principal components (PC1, PC2, and PC3) alongside their respective eigenvalues, which represent the proportion of variance explained by each principal component. For Factor 1 (Working Environment), the variables supervision, responsibility, achievement, working conditions, school and administration policies, and work itself exhibited different weights on PC1, indicating their varying contributions to the factor. Among these, supervision

demonstrated the highest weight, suggesting it has the strongest influence on the overall working environment. Similarly, for Factor 2 (Professional Growth), the variables recognition, interpersonal relationships, salary and benefits, supervision, and advancement showed differing weights on PC1, reflecting their varying degrees of importance. Recognition emerged as the most influential variable, indicating its substantial contribution to the professional growth factor. The first principal component (PC1) of each factor accounted for the majority of the variance, explaining 72.7% of the variance for Factor 1 and 69.2% for Factor 2. These results highlight the significant explanatory power of PC1 in capturing the essence of the variables contributing to each factor, thereby underscoring the importance of supervision in Factor 1 and recognition in Factor 2.

Table 5. Varying weights of the variables on the principal components (PCs) of the two factors.

	PC1	PC2	PC3	Uniqueness
Factor 1: Working Environment and Fulfillment				
Supervision	0.951	0.323	0.207	0.017
Responsibility	0.483	0.600	0.237	0.101
Achievement	0.381	0.358	0.376	0.099
Working Conditions	0.348	0.581	0.433	0.122
School and administration policies	0.198	0.702	0.177	0.069
Work Itself	0.142	0.187	0.725	0.021
<i>Eigenvalue</i>	3.151	0.451	0.303	
<i>Proportion</i>	0.727	0.104	0.070	
<i>Cumulative</i>	0.727	0.831	0.901	
Factor 2: Rewards and Social Relationships				
Recognition	0.688	0.458	0.180	0.137
Interpersonal Relations	0.590	0.068	0.233	0.138
Salary and Benefits	0.554	0.342	0.202	0.167
Supervision	0.370	0.335	0.902	0.006
Advancement	0.239	0.828	0.269	0.034
<i>Eigenvalue</i>	2.724	0.386	0.353	
<i>Proportion</i>	0.690	0.386	0.353	

	PC1	PC2	PC3	Uniqueness
<i>Cumulative</i>	0.690	0.098	0.090	

K-Means Clustering Analysis

The results of the K-Means Clustering algorithm are presented in Table 3, which reveals the optimal clustering solution for the data. Table 3 provides key clustering performance metrics, including the number of clusters, R-squared (R^2), Akaike Information Criterion (AIC), Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC), and Silhouette coefficient values. The Elbow Method Plot, depicted in Figure 1(a), serves as a visual tool to evaluate clustering performance and identify the optimal number of clusters. Based on this analysis, the optimal number of clusters was determined to be three, indicating that the data is best grouped into three distinct clusters. The R^2 value of 0.543 suggests that the clustering model accounts for approximately 54.3% of the variance, representing a moderate model fit. The AIC and BIC values, 210.860 and 256.650, respectively, reflect the relative quality of the model, with the optimized BIC value indicating the selection of a parsimonious model that balances complexity and fit. Furthermore, the Silhouette coefficient value of 0.260 suggests that the clusters are reasonably well-separated, with positive values closer to 1 indicating better-defined clusters.

Table 6. Model Summary: K-Means Clustering.

Clusters	N	R^2	AIC	BIC	Silhouette
3	34	0.543	210.860	256.650	0.260

The cluster analysis identified three distinct clusters with varying satisfaction levels, as detailed in Table 4. The t-SNE Cluster Plot, shown in Figure 1(b), provides a visualization of high-dimensional data in a reduced-dimensional space, effectively illustrating clustering structures and patterns. This plot confirms the presence of three distinct clusters, corresponding to those identified by the K-Means algorithm.

Figure 2. (a) Elbow Method Plot and (b) t-SNE Cluster Plot

Cluster 1 (Low Satisfaction), the smallest cluster with only two observations, exhibits minimal within-cluster heterogeneity (explained proportion: 0.037, within-sum-of-squares: 5.657) and is well-separated from other clusters, as indicated by a Silhouette score of 0.501 (Table 4). The uniformly negative cluster centers across all job satisfaction components reflect overall dissatisfaction. Cluster 2 (Moderate Satisfaction), the largest cluster with 17 observations, exhibits higher within-cluster heterogeneity (explained proportion: 0.581, within-sum-of-squares: 87.629) and weaker separation from other clusters, as reflected by a Silhouette score of 0.184. The cluster centers are generally neutral or slightly negative, reflecting moderate to low satisfaction, with notable dissatisfaction in components like "Recognition" (-0.446). Cluster 3 (High Satisfaction), comprising 15 observations, demonstrates moderate within-cluster heterogeneity (explained proportion: 0.382, within-sum-of-squares: 57.570) and a Silhouette score of 0.303, suggesting reasonable separation. This cluster is characterized by positive cluster centers across most components, such as "Responsibility" (0.766) and "Recognition" (0.704), indicating high satisfaction levels. These findings highlight the need for targeted interventions to address dissatisfaction in Cluster 1, the potential of Cluster 3 as a benchmark for best practices, and the opportunity to enhance specific components of satisfaction in Cluster 2.

Table 7. Cluster Information.

Variables	Cluster		
	1	2	3
Size	2	17	15
Percentage (%)	5.88%	50%	44.12%
Explained proportion within-cluster heterogeneity	0.037	0.581	0.382
Within the sum of squares	5.657	87.629	57.570
Silhouette score	0.501	0.184	0.303
Center School and Administration Policies (SAP)	-2.008	-0.278	0.582
Center Supervision (Sup)	-2.106	-0.341	0.668
Center Salary and Benefits (SaB)	-2.152	-0.265	0.588
Center Interpersonal Relations (IR)	-2.005	-0.292	0.598
Center Working Conditions (WC)	-2.534	-0.336	0.718
Center Work Itself (WI)	-3.201	0.089	0.326
Center Achievement (Ach)	-2.656	-0.246	0.633
Center Recognition (Rec)	-1.489	-0.446	0.704
Center Responsibility (Res)	-2.139	-0.424	0.766
Center Advancement (Adv)	-1.915	-0.311	0.608

5. DISCUSSION

Descriptive Statistics

Results show that job satisfaction for private teachers depends equally on intrinsic and extrinsic job satisfaction elements according to their sources of satisfaction, which is similar to the findings of Lleve et al. (2024). According to Mendoza (2024), teachers derive job satisfaction through fulfilling work experiences and recognition for their achievements because those elements create meaning in their career work. Baroudi et al. (2022) reported intrinsic satisfaction functions as a primary motivating factor that drives teacher performance. The combination of extrinsic motivators, which includes salary benefits alongside additional career opportunities and recognition rewards, leads teachers to develop a negative attitude toward their work and profession. Studies by Paais and Pattiruhu (2020) describe financial challenges and professional achievement recognition deficiencies as essential barriers to both teacher motivation and job

satisfaction. Staff supervision ratings and career growth accessibility show moderate approval from educators, yet prove insufficient regarding the provision of instructional and development services. Research results show that workplaces should maintain meaningful work assignments in addition to tackling issues with unbiased compensation packages and career mobility parameters. Overall, results reveal that working in a private school only offers to teachers a moderate satisfaction, in which salary and recognition are less appreciated. In that case, private educational institutions need to examine their current salary structures and recognition, as well as their succession planning, to build better teacher satisfaction levels while fighting against staff retention issues.

Exploratory Factor Analysis and Principal Component Analysis

The factor analysis and principal component analysis revealed that the sources of job satisfaction can be categorized into two factors: "Working Environment and Fulfillment" as factor 1 and "Rewards and Social Relationships" as factor 2. This result is parallel to the findings of some studies in the literature that job satisfaction is influenced by work environment, social relationship, and economic compensation (Keller & Semmer, 2013; Jian & Dalisay, 2017; Casinillo et al., 2021; Hungo et al., 2024). As for the "Working Environment and Fulfillment", it comprises the private teachers' working conditions, school and administration policies, responsibility, achievement, work itself, and supervision. It is worth noting that if the work environment is convenient and with a good atmosphere concerning the coworkers and heads, then it possibly affects their performances and their well-being. In the study of Lleve et al (2024), it is depicted that teachers who experience a stressful environment in school are more likely to be dissatisfied with their assigned tasks and have a lower level of job satisfaction. Administration policies are vital in a school since they direct the path of various stakeholders, including teachers. Now, if teachers do not feel fair and respected, then it affects their work quality and efficiency. In that case, the study suggests that school and administration policies must be enhanced to ensure the fairness and well-being of teachers and to improve their performance and job satisfaction. According to Casinillo et al. (2021), teachers' happiness in teaching is directly correlated to the school plan of action and the governance of the administration; hence, it is suggested that the institution's policies and management must be in accordance with the welfare of the workers. As mentioned by Zang et al. (2022), teachers' job satisfaction is influenced by workloads and responsibilities. In that case, teachers' productivity and contentment depend on the number of responsibilities, which implies that the heavier the workloads, the more likely they are to experience burnout and be unproductive. According to the paper by

Malquisto et al. (2023), it is portrayed that the work environment is considered conducive if the workload and responsibilities are not too heavy and teachers can be optimally productive and enthusiastic. In fact, the teachers' job satisfaction is boosted if they accomplish rewarding tasks and achieve in the work environment (Hoque et al., 2023). Likewise, Harrison et al. (2023) depicted that if teachers have achieved and accomplished their assigned tasks with good quality and in an orderly manner, then they are more likely to be satisfied with their job. Moreover, supervision from school leaders is important for teachers to be guided and directed in their tasks so that they can perform well and accordingly. Apparently, Altınok (2024) stated that supervision and guidance from school heads can lead to teaching quality and performance, which is positively associated with job satisfaction and well-being.

On the other hand, the "Rewards and Social Relationships" comprise recognition, interpersonal relations, salary and benefits, advancement, and supervision, which is another group source of job satisfaction among private teachers. It is worth noting that a teacher who receives awards or honors for their accomplishment in the institution can uplift their self-esteem, which motivates them to work and positively affects their job satisfaction and professional growth. In the study by Lim (2021), it is mentioned that to encourage teachers to do well and strengthen their morale in the work environment, their achievement and accomplished tasks must be awarded and be recognized. Awards for teachers can be a tangible form of appreciation to show them their accomplishments are worthy of being recognized and celebrated. According to Woosnam et al. (2020), teaching awards can inspire more teachers to continue in their endeavors and improve their productivity in the classroom setting. In addition, it is worth noting that if co-teachers and school heads are not hard to deal with or friendly in nature, then it is an encouragement to do their job peacefully in the work environment. Aguilar and Vina (2024) mentioned that a school's vision is attainable if the administration and co-teachers are supportive, follow employment ethics, and aim to work together to achieve a common goal. Moreover, good economic compensation for the teachers' work accomplishments, such as salary and other benefits, can motivate them to do their tasks accordingly. In fact, in the study by Casinillo and Dayap (2023), it is portrayed that income from a teaching job is one of the indicators of job satisfaction since it is the main reason for surviving economic activities in which they can provide for their needs and comfort. Plus, advancement opportunities in their teaching vocation, such as promotions, transfer to other educational positions, new technologies in the classroom, and advanced studies, among others, can interest the teachers and motivate them in their careers. Apparently, teachers are motivated to engage in new and innovative opportunities and advanced studies to enhance their teaching strategies and effectiveness in the classroom environment, which

develops their lifelong competence as educators (Juškevičienė et al., 2024; Kilag et al., 2024). Furthermore, the supervision of school heads is necessary for teachers' efficiency in work and aligning professional development in the teaching-learning process. In fact, supervision from school heads is in both factors (1 and 2) since it statistically influences the teachers' level of job satisfaction in a private institution. Again, Altınok (2024) emphasized that good management and direction in their teaching career can boost their confidence and motivate them to do their assigned task, which leads to professional growth.

K-means Clustering

Based on the result of *K-means* clustering, there are a few (5.88%) of the private teachers who do not perceive a job-satisfying experience in their current job. This result is consistent to the study of Hungo et al. (2024), which portrayed that there are teachers in a private school who are not satisfied to their job due to their heavy workloads and low salary. More likely, this implies that these teachers are not satisfied with the different sources of job satisfaction mentioned above. In that case, they pictured that their working environment is not conducive to them due to the nature of work, and they find themselves not productive, and not satisfied with the economic benefits. In the study by Casinillo et al. (2024), it is portrayed that if a teacher does not like the working environment, then they experience burnout in doing their task, which adversely affects their motivation and satisfaction. Apparently, Andriani et al. (2018) depicted that if a teacher is less satisfied in the working environment, they tend to perform low and, to a lesser extent, are motivated at their current job. In addition, according to Schaack et al. (2020), teachers who do not have enough fulfillment due to low salaries and poor benefits are more likely to feel burnout and dissatisfaction, which leads to turnover intention and less motivation in their careers. In addition, the *K-means* clustering revealed that about half (50%) of the private teachers are moderately satisfied with their jobs. This implies that these clusters of teachers are somehow satisfied with the working environment, salary and benefits, relationship with coworkers, and professional growth, among others. This result is consistent to the findings of Noori (2023) and Casinillo et al. (2025), which portrayed that there are existing private teachers who are moderately satisfied with their profession. Schaack et al. (2020) emphasized that because teachers are facing some difficulties on the job, problems with the school leaders, and low benefits, they tend to experience stress and burnout that somehow affects their eagerness and fulfillment in their assigned work. In fact, Lleve et al. (2024) portrayed that private teachers with a heavy workload and poor management can experience stress even if they are enjoying their teaching career, which

leads to lukewarm satisfaction with their job. Additionally, the job satisfaction of teachers is also affected by the negative dealings with their students and adverse relationships with co-workers, which affects their job performance, effectiveness, and satisfaction (Ololube, 2006; Aslam et al., 2016; Andriani et al., 2018; Casinillo et al., 2021). Moreover, the *K*-means clustering analysis depicted that there is a group of private teachers consisting of 44.12% of the total who are highly satisfied with their jobs. This means that this group of teachers is highly motivated in their working environment, they are comfortable with their workmates, and satisfied with their current salary and benefits. This result is parallel to the study of Akhtar et al. (2010), which also depicted that there are some teachers who are highly satisfied working in a private institution. Zang et al. (2022) mentioned that teachers who do not experience stress and exhaustion in their assigned tasks and when dealing with students are satisfied enough with their chosen career. In addition, Malquist et al. (2023) portrayed that satisfied teachers are doing their job with enjoyment and do not experience burnout. In that case, teachers are content with their environment, which makes them productive and enthusiastic at their assigned work. In the study of Harrison et al. (2023), it is mentioned that good and well-performing teachers are satisfied with the school as their work environment, in which they have a good relationship with the co-teachers, school leaders, and students.

6. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study aims to evaluate the different sources of job satisfaction among private teachers. It is concluded that, on average, teachers are moderately satisfied working in a private institution. Based on the result, there are teachers who are not fully satisfied with the working environment, salary, and benefits they get from their current career. Moreover, the factor analysis and principal component analysis revealed that the sources of job satisfaction can be grouped into two categories: (a) Working Environment and Fulfillment, and (b) Rewards and Social Relationships. This implies that some private teachers' job satisfaction is dependent on the nature of their workplace, and some are influenced with economic and professional growth. Furthermore, the *K*-means clustering portrayed that there are private teachers who have low job satisfaction, moderate satisfaction, and high satisfaction in their current jobs. Hence, the paper concluded that private teachers' job satisfaction can vary depending on the various sources, particularly in workloads, working environment and facilities, salary and benefits, and school management. The possible limitation of this study is that it does not apply statistical methods that determine the cause-and-effect phenomenon or elucidate the causal factors of job satisfaction. Hence, the current findings of this paper can be enhanced through the

application of regression analysis and structural equation modeling (SEM), which that determines the predictors of private teachers' satisfaction. Moreover, to strengthen the current results, it is highly recommended that a similar study be conducted with a large sample size and more private institutions. Furthermore, also for future studies, one may consider longitudinal studies to observe significant changes in teacher job satisfaction and qualitative studies for deeper insights into the sources of motivation in working at private institutions.

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